

A recurrence formula of Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$

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Abstract: A recurrence formula of Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ is derived or proved

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{-s} - 3^{-s} - 6^{-s}} \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k) \right]$$

Except a single pole at $s = 1$ and $\zeta(s) \rightarrow -\infty$ at $\text{Re}(s) \rightarrow -\infty$, it converges in the whole complex plane. It indicates no zeros on the vertical line $s = 1/2 + it$.

Introduction: Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ is defined in the region $\text{Re}(s) > 1$ in the whole complex plane $s = \sigma + it$ by the following equation

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad (1)$$

$\zeta(s)$ is finite when $\text{Re}(s) > 1$. It can be equivalently expressed as an infinite product over all the prime numbers. It was assumed that the distribution of the zeros of $\zeta(s)$ on the vertical line $s = 1/2 + it$ is related to the counting function of the prime numbers.

$$\zeta(s) = \prod_{\text{prime}} \frac{1}{1 - p^{-s}} \quad (2)$$

After analytic continuation to the whole complex plane, $\zeta(s)$ is supposed to satisfy the functional equation [1]

$$\zeta(s) = 2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-s) \zeta(1-s) \quad (3)$$

with the trivial zeros $\zeta(-2n) = 0$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$). The equation (3) can be considered as a transformation of center reflection from $\zeta(1-s)$ to $\zeta(s)$. The center of the reflection is at $(1/2, 0)$ in the complex plane. Because of this center reflection, the vertical line $s = 1/2 + it$ and the vertical strip $0 \leq \text{Re}(s) \leq 1$ become different from all other vertical lines and strips. The Riemann hypothesis states that all the non-trivial zeroes of $\zeta(s)$ are located on the vertical line $s = 1/2 + it$.

Here a recurrence formula of Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ is derived or proved. Except a single pole at $s = 1$ and $\zeta(s) \rightarrow -\infty$ at $\text{Re}(s) \rightarrow -\infty$, it converges in the whole complex plane $s = \sigma + it$. It shows no

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zeros on the vertical line $s = 1/2 + it$.

A recurrence formula of $\zeta(s)$: For the sake of convenience, all the derivations in this section are done in the region $\text{Re}(s) > 1$ without further specifying it. By employing the notation:

$$\zeta(s, f(n)) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{[f(n)]^s} \quad (4)$$

there are the following equations:

$$\zeta(s, n) = \zeta(s) \quad (5)$$

$$\zeta(s, 2n) = 2^{-s} \zeta(s) \quad (6)$$

$$\zeta(s, 3n) = 3^{-s} \zeta(s) \quad (7)$$

$$\zeta(s, 6n) = 6^{-s} \zeta(s) \quad (8)$$

$$\zeta(s, 2n - 1) = (1 - 2^{-s}) \zeta(s) \quad (9)$$

$$\zeta(s, 3n - 2) + \zeta(s, 3n - 1) = (1 - 3^{-s}) \zeta(s) \quad (10)$$

Beginning with equation (9) or (10) and then using equations (6) – (8), it will arrive at the equation:

$$1 + \zeta(s, 6n - 1) + \zeta(s, 6n + 1) = (1 - 2^{-s} - 3^{-s} + 6^{-s}) \zeta(s) \quad (11)$$

Using the binomial expansion

$$\left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^k \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \left(\pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^k \quad (12)$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} = 2 + 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} \quad (13)$$

it leads to

$$\zeta(s, 6n - 1) + \zeta(s, 6n + 1) = 2\zeta(s, 6n) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s + 2k, 6n) \quad (14)$$

By using the equation (8), it has

$$1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k, 6n) = (1-2^{-s}-3^{-s}-6^{-s})\zeta(s) \quad (15)$$

$$(1-2^{-s}-3^{-s}-6^{-s})\zeta(s) = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k) \quad (16)$$

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1-2^{-s}-3^{-s}-6^{-s}} \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k) \right] \quad (17)$$

The equation (17) can be written in the form

$$\zeta(s) = \zeta_0(s)(1 + \Delta(s)) \quad (18)$$

with the 0th approximation defined by

$$\zeta_0(s) = \frac{1}{1-2^{-s}-3^{-s}-6^{-s}} \quad (19)$$

and the correction term defined by

$$\Delta(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k) \quad (20)$$

The equations (17) and (1) are identical in the region $\text{Re}(s) > 1$

$$\frac{1}{1-2^{-s}-3^{-s}-6^{-s}} \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k) \right] \equiv \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad (21)$$

The asymptotic behavior of the equation (17) can be proved to be: (a) when $\sigma \rightarrow +\infty$, $\zeta_0(s) \rightarrow 1$ and $\Delta(s) \rightarrow 0$ and then $\zeta_0(s)\Delta(s) \rightarrow 0$ and (b) when $\sigma \rightarrow -\infty$, $\zeta_0(s)\Delta(s) \sim -(7/6)^{-\sigma} \rightarrow -\infty$. In contrast to the equation (1), the equation (17) converges in the region $\text{Re}(s) \leq 1$, except a single pole at $s = 1$ and $\zeta(s) \rightarrow -\infty$ at $\text{Re}(s) \rightarrow -\infty$. Therefore, the recurrence equation (17) is an explicit analytical expression of Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ when it is analytically continued to the whole complex plane.

$\zeta(s)$ on the real axis: From the equation (17), the $\zeta(s)$ on the real axis can be written in the form

$$\zeta(\sigma) = \frac{1}{1-2^{-\sigma}-3^{-\sigma}-6^{-\sigma}} \left[1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-\sigma-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \zeta(\sigma+2k) \right] \quad (22)$$

$$\zeta(\sigma) = \zeta_0(\sigma)(1 + \Delta(\sigma)) \quad (23)$$

$$\zeta_0(\sigma) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{-\sigma} - 3^{-\sigma} - 6^{-\sigma}} \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta(\sigma) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-\sigma-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1 - \sigma - m}{m} \right) \zeta(\sigma + 2k) \quad (25)$$

$\zeta(1 - |\varepsilon|) \rightarrow -\infty$, when $|\varepsilon| \rightarrow 0$ and $\zeta(1 + |\varepsilon|) \rightarrow +\infty$, when $|\varepsilon| \rightarrow 0$. $\zeta(\sigma) \sim -(7/6)^{-\sigma} \rightarrow -\infty$, when $\sigma \rightarrow -\infty$.

When $\sigma > 0$, the equation (25) will become

$$\Delta(\sigma) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2 \times 6^{-\sigma-2k} \Gamma(\sigma + 2k)}{\Gamma(2k + 1) \Gamma(\sigma)} \zeta(\sigma + 2k) \quad (\sigma > 0) \quad (26)$$

It converges as similar as the series of 6^{-2k} , and therefore truncation till 6^{-8} is a good approximation

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\sigma) \cong & \frac{\sigma(\sigma + 1)}{6^{\sigma+2} - 3^{\sigma+2} - 2^{\sigma+2} - 1} + \frac{\sigma(\sigma + 1)(\sigma + 2)(\sigma + 3)}{12(6^{\sigma+4} - 3^{\sigma+4} - 2^{\sigma+4} - 1)} + \\ & + \frac{\sigma(\sigma + 1)(\sigma + 2)(\sigma + 3)}{(6^{\sigma+2} - 3^{\sigma+2} - 2^{\sigma+2} - 1)(6^{\sigma+4} - 3^{\sigma+4} - 2^{\sigma+4} - 1)} + \\ & + \frac{\sigma(\sigma + 1)(\sigma + 2)(\sigma + 3)(\sigma + 4)(\sigma + 5)}{360(6^{\sigma+6} - 3^{\sigma+6} - 2^{\sigma+6} - 1)} + \\ & + \frac{\sigma(\sigma + 1)(\sigma + 2)(\sigma + 3)(\sigma + 4)(\sigma + 5)}{12(6^{\sigma+2} - 3^{\sigma+2} - 2^{\sigma+2} - 1)(6^{\sigma+6} - 3^{\sigma+6} - 2^{\sigma+6} - 1)} + \\ & + \frac{\sigma(\sigma + 1)(\sigma + 2)(\sigma + 3)(\sigma + 4)(\sigma + 5)(\sigma + 6)(\sigma + 7)}{20160(6^{\sigma+8} - 3^{\sigma+8} - 2^{\sigma+8} - 1)} \quad (\sigma > 0) \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

The following is a list of calculated values of $\zeta(s)$ with the known values in the parenthesis. It can be seen that the difference between the calculated values and the known values is less than 0.000001.

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(0.5) &= -1.460354306777 \quad (-1.460354508810) \\ \zeta(1.5) &= 2.612375195537 \quad (2.612375348686) \\ \zeta(2.0) &= 1.644934014908 \quad (1.644934066848) \\ \zeta(3.0) &= 1.202056887274 \quad (1.202056903160) \end{aligned}$$

$$\zeta(4.0) = 1.082323225163 \quad (1.082323233711)$$

When $\sigma \leq 0$, the equation (25) will become

$$\Delta(\sigma) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{2 \times 6^{-\sigma-2k} \Gamma(1-\sigma)}{\Gamma(2k+1)\Gamma(1-\sigma-2k)} \zeta(\sigma+2k) \quad (\sigma \leq 0) \quad (28)$$

From the equation (28), it is easy to obtain the following values

$$\Delta(0) = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\Delta(-1) = 0 \quad (30)$$

$$\zeta(0) = -\frac{1}{2} \quad (31)$$

$$\zeta(-1) = -\frac{1}{10} \quad (32)$$

$$\zeta(-2n) = 0 \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots) \quad (33)$$

The trivial zeros of the equation (17) are located at all the negative even points. Therefore, the recurrence equation (22) is the analytic continuation of $\zeta(s)$ on the real axis.

$\zeta(s)$ in the half complex plane $\text{Re}(s) > 0$: The binominal expansions will be employed separately on σ and t respectively. The equation (12) can be rewritten as

$$\left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} \pm \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1-s-m}{m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k-1} \quad (34)$$

$$\left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} = \left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} \quad (35)$$

$$\left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} \pm \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k-1} \quad (36)$$

$$\left(1 \pm \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} \pm \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1-it-m}{m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k-1} \quad (37)$$

Adopting the following notations:

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} = 2 + 2\Delta_+(\sigma) \quad (38)$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} = 2\Delta_-(\sigma) \quad (39)$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} = 2 + 2\Delta_+(it) \quad (40)$$

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} = 2\Delta_-(it) \quad (41)$$

it has

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-s} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} \quad (42)$$

$$= 2 + 2\Delta_+(\sigma) + 2\Delta_+(t) + 2(\Delta_+(\sigma)\Delta_+(t) + \Delta_-(\sigma)\Delta_-(t)) \quad (43)$$

$$= 2 + 2\Delta_+(\sigma) + \Delta(\sigma, t) \quad (44)$$

$$= 2 + 2\Delta\left(\frac{1}{6n}\right) \quad (45)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\left(\frac{1}{6n}\right) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1 - \sigma - m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1 - it - m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} + \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1 - \sigma - m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1 - it - m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k} + \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1 - \sigma - m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k-1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1 - it - m}{m} \right) \left(\frac{1}{6n}\right)^{2k-1} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

$$\Delta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{(6n)^s} \Delta\left(\frac{1}{6n}\right) \quad (47)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\Delta(s)}{2} &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k)}{6^{s+2k}} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k)}{6^{s+2k}} + \\
&+ \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k+2l)}{6^{s+2k+2l}} + \\
&+ \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l-1} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k+2l-2)}{6^{s+2k+2l-2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

Finally it can be obtained

$$\Delta(s) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k)}{6^{s+2k}} + \Delta(\sigma, t) \tag{49}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta(\sigma, t) &= 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k)}{6^{s+2k}} + \\
&+ 2 \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k+2l)}{6^{s+2k+2l}} + \\
&+ 2 \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l-1} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta(s+2k+2l-2)}{6^{s+2k+2l-2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{50}$$

The equation (49) is equivalent to the equation (20). Therefore, the equation (18), (19), (49) and (50) together are the analytic continuation of $\zeta(s)$, which is equivalent to the equation (17).

The approximation of the equation (49) can be expressed as

$$\Delta(s) \cong 2\Delta_+(\sigma) + \Delta(\sigma, t) + \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)\Delta(\sigma+2, t)}{6^{s+2} - 3^{s+2} - 2^{s+2} - 1} \tag{51}$$

with

$$2\Delta_+(\sigma) \cong \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)}{6^{s+2} - 3^{s+2} - 2^{s+2} - 1} + \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)(\sigma+2)(\sigma+3)}{12(6^{s+4} - 3^{s+4} - 2^{s+4} - 1)} +$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)(\sigma+2)(\sigma+3)}{(6^{s+2} - 3^{s+2} - 2^{s+2} - 1)(6^{s+4} - 3^{s+4} - 2^{s+4} - 1)} + \\
& + \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)(\sigma+2)(\sigma+3)(\sigma+4)(\sigma+5)}{360(6^{s+6} - 3^{s+6} - 2^{s+6} - 1)} + \\
& + \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)(\sigma+2)(\sigma+3)(\sigma+4)(\sigma+5)}{12(6^{s+2} - 3^{s+2} - 2^{s+2} - 1)(6^{s+6} - 3^{s+6} - 2^{s+6} - 1)} + \\
& + \frac{\sigma(\sigma+1)(\sigma+2)(\sigma+3)(\sigma+4)(\sigma+5)(\sigma+6)(\sigma+7)}{20160(6^{s+8} - 3^{s+8} - 2^{s+8} - 1)}
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta(\sigma, t) & \cong 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta_0(s+2k)}{6^{s+2k}} + \\
& + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta_0(s+2k+2l)}{6^{s+2k+2l}} + \\
& + 2 \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l-1} \frac{1-\sigma-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k-1} \frac{1-it-m}{m} \right) \frac{\zeta_0(s+2k+2l-2)}{6^{s+2k+2l-2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

Using the following expansions

$$\zeta_0(s+2k+2l) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{-s-2k-2l} - 3^{-s-2k-2l} - 6^{-s-2k-2l}} \tag{54}$$

$$\zeta_0(s+2k+2l) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (2^{-s-2k-2l} + 3^{-s-2k-2l} + 6^{-s-2k-2l})^n \tag{55}$$

$$\zeta_0(s+2k+2l) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{n_1+n_2=n \\ n_1, n_2=0}} \frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! (n-n_1-n_2)!} (2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2})^{-s-2k-2l} \tag{56}$$

$$\frac{\zeta_0(s+2k+2l)}{6^{s+2k+2l}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{n_1+n_2=n \\ n_1, n_2=0}} \frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! (n-n_1-n_2)!} (2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1})^{-s-2k-2l} \tag{57}$$

in combination with following equations

$$\Delta(\sigma, t) = 2\Delta_+(t) + 2(\Delta_+(\sigma)\Delta_+(t) + \Delta_-(\sigma)\Delta_-(t)) \quad (58)$$

$$= (1 + (\Delta_+(\sigma))(2\Delta_+(t)) + \Delta_-(\sigma)(2\Delta_-(t)) \quad (59)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\sigma, t) &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \right) \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} - 2 \right) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \right) \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

$$\Delta(\sigma, t) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \left(\left(1 - \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} - 1 \right) + \left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-\sigma} \left(\left(1 + \frac{1}{6n}\right)^{-it} - 1 \right) \quad (61)$$

then it can obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\sigma, t) &\cong \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_1, n_2=0}^{n_1+n_2=n} \frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! (n - n_1 - n_2)!} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} - 1} \right)^{\sigma} \times \right. \\ &\times \left(\left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} - 1} \right)^{it} - \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1}} \right)^{it} \right) + \\ &\left. + \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} + 1} \right)^{\sigma} \left(\left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} + 1} \right)^{it} - \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1}} \right)^{it} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

The equations (18), (19), (51), (52) and (62) are the approximate analytic continuation of $\zeta(s)$ in the region $\text{Re}(s) > 0$ in the complex plane.

Another approach for $\zeta(s)$ in the half complex plane $\text{Re}(s) > 0$: The method used to derive the equation (62) can be applied to equation (20) and then have the approximation

$$\Delta(s) \cong \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta_0(s+2k) \quad (63)$$

$$\Delta(s) \cong \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n_1, n_2=0}^{n_1+n_2=n} \frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! (n - n_1 - n_2)!} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} - 1} \right)^s + \right.$$

$$+ \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} + 1} \right)^s - 2 \left(\frac{1}{2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1}} \right)^s \} \quad (64)$$

To iteratively substituting $\zeta(s+2k)$ in the equation (20) by the equation (17),

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(s) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta_0(s+2k) [1 + \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k-2l} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta(s+2k+2l)] \end{aligned} \quad (65)$$

and the approximation

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(s) &\cong \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta_0(s+2k) [1 + \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 2 \times 6^{-s-2k-2l} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta_0(s+2k+2l)] \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(s) &\cong 2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta_0(s+2k) + \\ &+ 4 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 6^{-s-2k} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2k} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} 6^{-s-2k-2l} \left(\prod_{m=1}^{2l} \frac{1-s-m}{m} \right) \zeta_0(s+2k) \zeta_0(s+2k+2l) \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

Using the following notations

$$f(n) = 2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} \quad (68)$$

$$g_{-1}(n, f(m)) = 2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} (f(m) - 1) \quad (69)$$

$$g_0(n, f(m)) = 2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} f(m) \quad (70)$$

$$g_{+1}(n, f(m)) = 2^{n_1} 3^{n_2} 6^{n-n_1-n_2+1} (f(m) + 1) \quad (71)$$

the equation (67) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta(s) &\cong \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{n_1+n_2=n \\ n_1, n_2=0}} \frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! (n-n_1-n_2)!} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{f(n)-1} \right)^s + \left(\frac{1}{f(n)+1} \right)^s - 2 \left(\frac{1}{f(n)} \right)^s \right\} + \\
&+ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{n_1+n_2=n \\ n_1, n_2=0}} \frac{n!}{n_1! n_2! (n-n_1-n_2)!} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{\substack{m_1+m_2=m \\ m_1, m_2=0}} \frac{m!}{m_1! m_2! (m-m_1-m_2)!} \times \\
&\times \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{g_{-1}(n, f(m))-1} \right)^s + \left(\frac{1}{g_{-1}(n, f(m))+1} \right)^s - 2 \left(\frac{1}{g_{-1}(n, f(m))} \right)^s + \right. \\
&+ \left(\frac{1}{g_{+1}(n, f(m))-1} \right)^s + \left(\frac{1}{g_{+1}(n, f(m))+1} \right)^s - 2 \left(\frac{1}{g_{+1}(n, f(m))} \right)^s - \\
&\left. - 2 \left(\frac{1}{g_0(n, f(m))-1} \right)^s - 2 \left(\frac{1}{g_0(n, f(m))+1} \right)^s + 4 \left(\frac{1}{g_0(n, f(m))} \right)^s \right\} \quad (72)
\end{aligned}$$

The equation (64), or (72) for a better approximation, in combination with the equations (18) and (19) is another approximate expression of $\zeta(s)$ in the half complex plane $\text{Re}(s) > 0$.

References:

- [1] B. Riemann, "Über die Anzahl der Primzahlen unter einer gegebenen Grösse", Monatsberichte der Berliner Akademie, (1859)